

Management Role in Improving the Quality of Services and Maintaining Their Excellence in the Market Using Electronic Marketing: A Field Study on Zain Jordan Communication Company

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Abstract

This study aimed at identifying the role of management in the improvement of services qualities and maintaining their excellence in the market using electronic marketing. Data were collected using a self-prepared questionnaire and administering it to Zain company's employees, as it is deemed the appropriated method for the current study. Results showed the following; (1) Management has a role in increasing customers through sustaining services quality, with a high degree, (2) Management assigns customers a role in formulating quality strategy and their suggestions are taken in account when formulating company strategy. (3) Electronic marketing strategy contribution in constructing an effective role in customer's satisfaction at a high degree, (4) Management regarded customers as the central axis on which it depends to achieve quality strategy, (5) Employees while working electronically, emphasize the distinguished loyalty to their company, and improving its image among customers. (6) Focusing on electronic marketing is one of the most important strategies used by management to minimize money waste and improve its image among customers. However, the study suggested the need for applying quality principles, particularly in organizations seeking competitive superiority over other organizations, as well as focusing on customers satisfaction since relatively high quality will achieve high degree of customers satisfaction, gaining thereby, new customers and accomplishing complete satisfaction, which in turn, will create higher profits, due to its maintenance of customers.

Keywords: *Customers relationships management, Quality management, Electronic marketing, Customers service, Total quality*

Introduction

Current age is the age of information and communication where the development of communications was accompanied by the invention of high storage capacity storing means, under the availability of and spread of internet access. Consequently, the world shifted from industrial to informational society. However, there is no doubt that excellence and creativity are not limited to what is materialistic as a new process or new product; but it spreads over into new services and methods as well as the business model. The wide spread of internet businesses and the explosive spread of dot come, resulted in the appearance of internet-based creativity on a large scale in most countries, these inventions included, among another thing, one-click – shopping as an example of e-marketing. Consequently Amazon.com succeeded in directing an effective business model based on marketing of books in others stores through one internet click, which markets other stored books on the internet, worldwide, creating a new service and market; rather than stores with long books shelves advertisements, bulletins and precious marketing guides ,it established elegant and effective web pages to achieve quick use by new customers. Current markets are characterized by fierce competition among organizations, as an effort to fulfill customer's needs and demands as well as satisfying them by making them enjoy competitive advantages that allow them maintain their positions in places where they work.

Moreover the study introduced some conclusions and suggestion consistent with analysis results the most important of which that the development of marketing methods realized great results, where it provided better services through ice-breaking of routine procedures complexities. Moreover, electronic marketing allowed the possibility to access all services and easy meeting customer demands, while the study recommended the need for applying quality principles, particularly in organizations seeking competitive superiority over other organizations, as well as focusing on customer's satisfaction, since relatively high quality will lead to high customers satisfaction, resulting, therefore, to gaining new customers as well as achieving perfect satisfaction, which, in its turn, will result in higher profits.

A brief overview of Zain communication, company, Jordan

In a world overwhelmed by internet and development of accelerated modern technologies in communication methods and information industries, electronic business solution services and in a world in which a computer mouse click separates customers all over the world, challenge, therefore, does not lie in searching for new customer, only, but in understanding and realizing current customers demands as well as maintaining them, also. Zain, Jordanian communication company for mobile phones, [previously known as fast link], made a revolution in Jordanian communications markets, by its introduction of GSM services for mobile communication. In 1995, Zain Jordan revolutionized telecommunications in Jordan by introducing GSM mobile services into the country. Zain quickly became the foremost telecom company in Jordan, a position that it kept to this day through a far sighted policy of investment in adopting cutting edge technology to provide state of the art services to customers. Since its inception, Zain Jordan has tallied subscriber growth at an exceptional rate, with the number of subscribers around 5,903 million subscribers in the kingdom. Through about 6325 cell sites, Zain covers the entire populated area of Jordan. Aiming at maintaining its leading position in the marketing, Zain acquired in 2014 the license to provide the Fourth Generation services “LTE” for the first time in the kingdom, where these services provide up to 150 Mb per second. Zain launched LTE services to include all the governorates of the Kingdom in the first quarter of 2015. And among its products’ portfolio, Zain launched “Zain Fiber” services to enrich its customers ‘experience that is driven by (FTTH – Fiber-To-The-Home) technology that provides premium quality and stable internet with high speed. Zain Jordan pioneered in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), by launching and supporting various national initiatives that go beyond developing the telecom sector, as Zain is considered the main supporter for several sectors: Education, Youth, and Health, Sports, Environment and philanthropy. Zain is also considered as one of the Jordanian economy pillars as it embraces around one thousand employees and provide thousands of indirect job opportunities and it was the operator of choice for more than 5.903 million Jordanian customers. Aiming at supporting entrepreneurship realm in Jordan, Zain inaugurated Zain Innovation Campus (ZINC), in November 2014; and it is the first of its kind across the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, where Zain provides Jordanian entrepreneurs and startups with all the requirements to develop and to transform their creative and innovative ideas into productive projects that shall be marketed locally, regionally and globally. Located at King Hussein Business Park, ZINC is equipped with the latest technology and facilities and services, in addition to providing consulting and guidance, and the opportunity to access a network of nearly 90 strategic partners, representing world's leading technology corporates, businesses and startups, and companies interested in embracing creative ideas from various sectors. Worth mentioning that Zain Group acquired Zain Jordan, in January 2003, in what was considered the largest single acquisition in the Middle East region, and the largest private sector investment in Jordan.

Research Problem

Business organization using electronic marketing, in their relationships with customers and increasing their ability in knowing and understanding current customers needs, as well as identifying customers previously favored services along with those will be favored in the future, which will result in increased customer trust a part from its role in increasing satisfaction and comfort, since, after the introduction of electronic concept, there has been a notable and clear interest in customers, and this interest was within various approaches including customers maintenances satisfaction according to the relationship between Zein Jordanian communications company and its customers, hence the main problem of the current study, lies in the humble exerted effort by part of this corporation.

Consequently, the current research problem came in two basic domains; the strategic role of quality management, from one hand, and electronic customer relationship management, from the other, therefore the study problem lies in answering the following research questions:

- What is the role of management in increasing the number of customers by maintaining and developing its quality?

- To what extent electronic marketing strategy contribute in building an effective role in customer's satisfaction?

Research Hypothesis

- There is a statistically significant relationship between customer relationships while maintaining quality.
- There is a statistically significant relationship between electronic marketing process and customer satisfactions.

Research Objectives

Customer is the basic partner of the corporation, hence, it is necessary to create mutual benefit between these two parties, on the basis of customer relations management, so it is necessary to introduce products characterized with quality, compared with competitors, and knowing this through the actual participation between customers and organization to measure final customer satisfaction so as to identify benefits achieved to customer and which will achieve the final value, knowing, at the same time, the degree of customer's loyalty to products introduced by the company, identifying appropriate ways for maintaining customers, through the study of satisfaction, loyalty, value and identifying general strategy, and in quality domain, in particular, as well as identifying which principles has the pioneering role in establishing differentiation and increasing organization profits.

Significance of the Study

The study significance stems from the importance of its subject, since electronic marketing enables organizations to comprehend modern technologies in communication and information systems domain, furthermore its application makes these organization, more flexible and ability to transfer and apply the most advanced technologies and benefit from. Also theoretical importance of the study lies in informing customers about electronic marketing characteristics and advantages of its application as well as major obstacles hindering the efficacy of this application, and that its application will result in providing citizens with better services.

However, our study has some basic themes and points of importance, which were classified into three major themes:

Customer level Importance:

- Highlighting the strategic role of customers in quality strategic plans at the whole organization.
- Identifying and measurement of final customer satisfaction.
- Specifying customer's achieved benefits which will realize his final value.
- Identifying customer loyalty degree for products introduced by the organization.

Organizational Level Importance:

1. Specifying appropriate methods to retain customers through the study of satisfaction, loyalty and value.
2. Identifying general strategies, especially in total quality management and which principles have the pioneering role in establishing differentiation and increasing organizational profits.
3. Identifying customer's psychological and behavioral influential factors through engaging them in quality plans.

Customer and Organizational Shared Importance:

1. Customer is the primary organization's partner, therefore mutual benefits, between the two parties, should be built on customer relationships management basis.
2. Introducing products characterized with high quality in relation with competitors through actual sharing between both parties (organization and customer).
3. Analysis and study of opinions and suggestions from customers to the organization through marketing research to identify customer's satisfaction, loyalty and value, and possibilities for establishing and improving it.

Procedural Definitions:

Customers relationships management

Modern studies focus on assigning broader meaning and definitions to customers relations management (CRM), where authors did not agree on setting a specified definition for (CRM), (Abu Anaja 2008) defined it as the art and science of attracting new customers while retaining current ones, while achieving needed growth for transactions with beneficiary customers, however (Swift 2000) defined (CRM) as an approach to understanding customer's behavior through extensive communication to improve performance represented in attracting customer, retaining him and increasing his loyalty and profitability. (Forss and Stone 2001), from the other hand defined (CRM) as companies use of its capabilities in the domain of research methods, technology, and electronic commerce of the relationships with customers. Also, (Mendoza et al., 2007) defined (CRM) as a strategy containing human, an technological aspects along with processes followed by the organization to put certain decision into practice, as they consider this concept to include a collection of activities aimed at enhancing and improving relationships with customers, understanding their various needs and wants, furthermore, (Ferrell and Hartline 2011) defined (CRM) as a work philosophy that aids in specifying and maximizing customers value in ways that motivate customers to maintain their loyalty. However, (Loveloock and Wirtz 2011) defined (CRM) as empowering and picking customers information and giving it back to him with various communication points; from the other part, (Kotler and Keller 2012) defined (CRM) as Managerial process of caring about detailed information about customers and all organization points with customers, so as to maximize his loyalty, as (CRM) allows companies to provide excellent service, just in time, to customers through optimal use of individual information, based on what organizations know about each customer's value.

We can, from the above discussion, that authors differ greatly in defining customer relation management, where everyone defined it according to his point of view, however, in light of the above definitions some appropriate, definition, for the study purposes, was reached and this definition, stated that (CRM) is a comprehensive, practical and integrated strategy between an organization and stakeholders, in general, and customers in particular, based on negotiation, consultation and mutual trust to retain and achieve customers value.

Quality Management

(Assaqaf 1998) stated that multiple and different writings perspectives on quality subject resulted in great differences in its definition, in spite of increased interest in it, therefore, a comprehensive and clear definition of quality within each organization, must be controlled, so as to make possible the measurement of quality and apply it on work. However, quality can be defined as follows:

- Product based definition: (Al-Bakri, 2003): quality definition from this perspective is based on the organization production of a good or providing a service with high excellent proficiency, so it becomes able, through it, to fulfill its customers needs and wants in a way consistent with their expectations, and to achieve their satisfaction and happiness among them, which can be achieved by

preset measures to produce a product or provide a service as well as the establishment of excellent feature in it.

- Definition: (Al-Bakri 2003) defined quality as a personal matter based on user preferences required in a product or service and products that provide highest satisfaction of these preferences, are considered among products with highest qualities.
- Manufacturing based definition: cost, and prices based quality definition depends on several other characteristics, while buying decision depends on value and quality, where higher quality product does not, usually, mean the best value, where best quality describes the product or the service with better buy.
- Total quality definition, where quality means product or service ability to fulfill or exceed customer expectations, hence means customer getting something in exchange of what he paid to get its benefits, and it one of major reason behind reduced quality in our organization, might be due to the focus of most organizations on cost and productivity rather than their interest in quality.
- Electronic marketing: is the employment of internet as a communication channel for promoting goods and services..., however, it can also be defined as a wide and integrated concept covering advertisements, customer contact, enhancement of the organizational commercial position to draw customer attention, gaining and retaining him for the longest possible period.
- Customers service: a collection of activities aiming at enhancing customer's satisfaction, that is the feeling that the product got customer satisfaction, or the process by which, customers needs and expectation, are met, through the provision of a high quality service that results in customers satisfaction.

Research Methodology

To achieve the study objectives, and based on its nature, descriptive analytical approach, which expressed social phenomena under study, was used, however, there actually existed quantitative and qualitative expressions, which is not confined to the description of the studied phenomenon or collecting information for the investigation of its various aspects, but which goes beyond that to the analysis and interpreting the phenomenon, and achieving conclusions that contribute to the specification of the appropriate methods for developing and improving the status quo (Assaf, 2002). Given the multiple approaches of the descriptive analytic approach, social survey approach, using comprehensive survey method, was employed, as it is the appropriate approach for the phenomena under study, as it enabled researchers to collect information needed for answering research questions and achieving its objectives and because it's a way used in descriptive studies to describe or changing a certain status in a period of time specified with the study period (Al- Fawwall, 1982). And because it investigates the status or phenomena under investigation and expressed it quantitatively or qualitatively, where qualitative expressions describes the phenomena and clarify its features, however, quantitative expression gives us a numerical description showing the quantity or volume of this phenomenon volume as it exists in reality (Obeidat, 1995).

Study Limitations

The study was confined on employees at Zain Jordanian Communication Company, in order to measure management role in improving services provided and maintaining their superiority in the market, using electronic marketing.

Study Population

Study population consisted of all employees working for Zein communication company, Jordan, questionnaires were distributed to Employees.

Study Sample

The study sample consisted of (170) employees at Zein Communication Company, with a 100% return rate, however after sorting, 159 questionnaires were deemed valid for statistical analysis.

Study Instrument

Primary sources: questionnaire, as a tool for collecting field data needed for this study, the questionnaire was designed in a manner suitable with the study nature and objectives.

Secondary sources: books, and scientific references related to the study subject were consulted.

Literature Review

Al Sakarneh (2012) conducted a study aiming at identifying the extent to which Jordanian cellular communications companies are interested in applying work ethics in the following domain: respect of laws and regulations, justice and non biasing, speed and mastery, and time respect, as well as identifying difference level in subjects perception of work ethics dimensions due to their personal characteristics, the study also aimed at assessing the effect of work ethics on the management of mental image, data was used to collect data from managers and employees at central centers; the study revealed the following.

Jordan cellular communication companies showed high level of interest in work ethics in its four dimensions, however, no statistically significant differences in subjects perceptions of work ethics due to their demographics, but a significant effect of work ethics as a whole, in the management of mental image as a whole, was found. Also the study showed no statistically significant effect of work ethics dimensions as a whole on self mental image or on self mental image of justice and non bias, and time respect domains.

Moreover work ethics as a whole have no significant effect on perceived mental image, however, work ethics domains related to laws and regulation respect and speed and mastery have a significant effect on perceived mental image.

Al-Hindawi et al (2010) conducted a study aiming at identifying the extent to which companies adopted marketing ethics and the effectiveness of its commercial advertisement, and their effect on consumer knowledge. The study population included employees from both Zein and orange companies, from whom a simple random sample of (70) employees, divided equally between the two companies, was selected. Descriptive statistics consisting of frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviation of the instruments, as well as one sample T – test, multiple regression analysis, and internal consistency (Cronbach alpha) test were used. Results revealed the following: both companies used valid slogan in their promotional campaigns and both employed social marketing concept in several domains including environmental and sportive ones. However, in the general services domain, application of social responsibility by communication companies influence marketing on consumer knowledge.

Aghazadeh (1999) study provided an analysis of human resources management and its requirements in the new century and focused on technological future challenges and globalization as effective and directly factors in human resources domain. The study suggested that human resources specialists ought to enhance organizational capabilities in recruiting and retaining qualified individuals.

Moran and Average (1999) study showed the change management is a continuous process for organization wishing to keep up with technological and other advancement, as change in the digital world is characterized with a high degree and took the non standardized approach, and has no clear beginning or end or accurately defined therefore organization, should be equipped with readiness and willingness to keep up with and development.

Rowley (1999) conducted a study aimed at identifying the importance of knowledge management in the digital world and highlighting basic issues influencing the effectiveness of executing knowledge management as a vital asset of financial, human and other assets, and as such organization, need to perceive

knowledge value in their work domains and activities and working on building appropriate knowledge inventory and improving method of knowledge environment and enhance them.

Haedstar & Bull company (2001) Haedstar conducted a study in cooperation with Bull company which included forty countries in collaboration with the world Bank, united nations, governments, international business organizations, academicians, non-profit organizations, and trade unions. The study showed the importance of keeping up with electronical and digital changes in economic, management and society in general, and its results showed that internet is an influential factor in market globalization and global income growth. As some experts estimate that electronic commerce will constitute 2-5 % of global sales by 2003; Also internet will influence supply, cost, customers relations, and organizational structure of industries, which will require root changes of classical techniques in each o governments and business organization. Furthermore, it is necessary to develop individuals skills and knowledge to fit electronical developments and advancements.

Statistical Analysis and Results Discussion

This section included results presentation, which aimed at identifying management role in improving services quality and marinating their excellence in market by using electronic marketing at Zein Communications Company - Jordan. It also included a description of subjects demographic such as gender, age, educational qualification, experience years, and job title. SPSS (Statistical package for social sciences) program was used to compute means, standard deviations for all the instrument items and for instrument as a whole, Meanwhile frequencies, percentage of personal variables for the sample of the study. Following is the results presentations:

-Personal information:

A random sample from the study population, totaling for (159) individuals. Tables 1-5 show their distribution on these variables.

Sample distribution by gender.

Table (1) Sample distribution by gender

Gender (Sex)	Frequency	Percentage
Male	77	%45.3
Female	82	%54.7
Total	159	%100

Table (1) showed that the majority of the study sample were females forming (%54.7) while males percentage was %45.3).

Table (2) Sample distribution by age

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 25 Years	52	43.4%
25-30 Years	46	35.8%
31-35 Years	34	17%
36 and more	27	3.8%
Total	159	100%

Table (2) showed that the highest frequency on age variable was 52 with 43.4% and was for the age group less than 25 years, followed by age group 25-30 years with a frequency of (46) and 35.8% however the lowest frequency was for the age group 36 and more with a frequency of (27) and 3.8%.

Table (3) Sample distribution by educational qualification

Education qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Community college Diploma	37	22.6%
bachelor	77	56.6%
Masters	35	18.9%
Doctorate	10	1.9%
Total	159	100%

Table (3) showed that the highest frequency on educational qualification variable was (77) with 56.6% and was for educational qualification bachelor degree, followed by community college diploma with 37 and 22.6%. However the lowest frequency was for doctoral degree with a frequency of 10 and a percentage of 1.9%.

Table (4) Sample distribution by years of experience variable.

Years of experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 Years	74	47.2%
6-10 years	53	39.6%
11-15	32	13.2%
Total	159	100%

Table (4) showed that the highest frequency for years of experience was (74) with (47.2%) and was for the 1-5 years of experience category, followed by 6-10 years of experience category with (53) and 39.6% however least frequency was for 11-15 years of experience category with (32) and 13.2%.

Table (5) Sample distribution by Job title

Job title	Frequency	Percentage
Sales and Marketing	61	60.4%
Management	34	7.5%
Reception	24	5.7%
Accounting	40	26.4%
Total	159	100%

Table (5) showed that the highest frequency for job title was (61) with 60.4% and was for sales and marketing category, followed by Accounting with 40 and 26.4% however the lowest frequency was for reception with 24 and 5.7%.

-Hypothesis testing

H₁: Management has a role in increasing number of customers, through maintenance and development of quality.

Testing this hypothesis Means and Standard deviations, for all management role in increasing number of customers through maintenance and development of quality, items, table 6 showed these results. Moreover One sample T – Test for comparing Means with the Standard score (3), were performed, in order to calculate value and Statistical Significance for this domain, as well as their total score, and results are displayed in table (7).

Table (6) Means and Standard Deviations for subjects responses on each item of management role in increasing numbers of customer domain and their total score:

Item No.	Item	Rank	Means	S.D	Estimation degree
1	Organization gives customers a role information quality strategy and take their suggestions into account when setting strategic plan	1	4.35	0.78	high
2	Organization considers customers as it is indirect partner, and so it is necessary to fulfill his complete satisfaction.	6	4.15	0.79	high
3.	Organization considers customer as the basis axis to depend on for the achievement of quality strategy.	1	4.35	0.85	high
4.	Organization considers customer as the pushing force for working on quality improvement and productivity increase hen considering his opinions and suggestions.	4	4.16	0.93	high
5.	Organization uses many means to retain customers	3	4.30	0.97	high
6.	Organization listens, to customers opinion and suggestions, carefully.	15	3.90	1.13	high
7.	Organization urges its employees to put themselves in customer's shoes.	17	3.86	1.24	high
8.	Organization works on the continuity of communication with customers.	10	3.96	1.07	high
9.	Continuous improvement in the service provided one of the important strategies adopted by organization to retain its customers.	9	4	1.07	high
10.	Continuous improvement became an incentive stimulating employees to provide high quality services.	4	4.16	0.95	high
11.	You have the ability to specify and analyze the problems and knowing what is to be improved.	12	3.94	1.00	High
12.	Organization always documents what is achieved while comparing previous performance with current one.	11	3.96	0.96	High
13.	Employees have the ability to develop alternative solutions and conduct continuous improvement in service provision.	7	4.07	1.03	High
14.	There exists a clear and understood quality policy, which everyone can apply in the organization.	12	3.94	0.96	High
15.	Your company uses objective standards for measuring employees performance first of which improving provided services quality	8	4.03	1.14	High
16.	Most customers prefer your services and offers over these of other organization.	18	3.84	1.39	High
17.	Performing the service correctly from the first time at the appropriate time is one of the dominant values in the organization.	14	3.92	1.15	High
18.	You focus on raising the level of services provided to customer on a continuous basis and don't leave competitors exceed your company.	16	3.88	1.20	High
19.	Having the customer getting the service with minimum cost, time, and effort is among your company priorities. Questionnaire as a whole. management role in increasing number of customers through maintenance and development of quality	19	3.79	1.29	High

Table (6) revealed that the highest mean was 4.35 and was for item (1.3) which stated "Organization give customers a role in formulating quality strategy and is taken in account when setting the strategic plan" and organization considered customer the central axis to depend on in achieving quality strategy" respectively, followed by item (5) with a mean of (4.30) and stated "Organization used many ways (Means) to retain customers, followed by items (4.10) with a mean of 4.16, and they state Organization considers customers as the pushing force to work on quality improvement and productivity increase when taking his a pinions and suggestion into account and continuous improvement became on incentive that stimulates employees to produce at high quality, respectively. However low ever lowest mean came for item (19) which stated have customer get the service at minimum cost, time and effort is among company's priorities, with a mean of 3.79.

However, Management role in increasing number of customers through maintenance and advancement of quality domain got a mean score of 4.03, indicating that management has a a role in increasing number of customers through maintain and advancement of quality with a high degree.

Moreover, one sample T- test, to identify the statically significance of management role in increasing number of customers through maintaining and advancing quality, was used, and table (7) displayed these results.

Table (7)

Hypothesis	Mean	SD	T value	D F	Sig.	Results
Management has a role in increasing numbers customers through maintain and advising quality	4.03	0.51	14.53	158	0.00	Accepted

From table (7), we can see that mean rating of the management role in increasing number of customers through maintaining and advancing quality doming quality domain, was 4.03 with a standard deviation of 0.051 and high rating degree. However when comparing mean rating with the student score (3), T value was 14.53, which is a statistically significant value at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) level, hence the hypotheses was accepted, consequently, management has a role in increasing number of customers through maintain and advancing quality with a high degree.

Second hypothesis: Electronic marketing strategy contribute to constructing an effective role in customer satisfaction.

Means, and standard deviations, for all items of electronic marketing strategy contribution in the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction were computed, and table (8) displays these means and standard deviations, father more, one sample T. test to identify means differences and the standard score (3) to calculate to value and statistical significance of this domain was also employed, and its results are displayed in table (9).

Table (8) Means, and Standard Deviations of the items of the contribution of electronic marketing strategy to the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction domain and domain as a whole.

Item No.	Item	Rank	Mean	SD	Rating degree
1	Focusing on electronic marketing is among the important strategies used by the company to minimize money waste.	3	4.15	1.04	high
2.	Focusing on electronic marketing is the real interpreter of customer needs and wants.	8	3.92	1.01	high
3.	Electronic marketing is elastic allowing therefore, its change according to customary tests change.	9	3.83	1.10	High
4.	Electronic marketing is interconnected chain of activities aiming at achieving higher value for the customer.	4	4.13	1.00	High
5.	Management employs certain methods and strategies to keep up with advancements occurring in communication domain and new offers introduction.	5	4.05	1.06	High
6.	Your company mission is embedded in achieving customer's satisfaction through continuous improvement in electronically provided services quality and superiority.	1	4.30	1.06	High
7.	In your electronic – based work, you emphasize on distinctive loyalty to your company and improving its image in customers minds.	2	4.16	1.03	High
8.	Electronic quick response to customers objections, and dealing with and treating them instantly.	9	3.83	1.08	High
9.	You give customers a good impression that his visit to the company site and electronically dealing with him are important aspects for you.	7	3.94	1.21	High
10.	Your electronically provided services are unique and distinct, satisfying, thereby, customer and possess more dimension than competitors. Domain as a whole.	6	3.98	1.15	high

Table (8) showed that highest mean was 4.30 and was on it item (6) which states electronic marketing strategy contribution to the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction, followed by item (7) which states in your work, you emphasize electronically on distinctive loyalty to your company and improving its image in customers mind so, with a mean of (4.16), followed by item (1), which states Focusing on electronic marketing is among the important strategies employed by the company to minimize money waste, with a mean of 4.15. However, Lowest means went to item 3,8, which state electronic marketing is flexible (elastic), allowing its change according to customers tastes change and speed electronic response to customers objections, dealing with and treating them instantly respectively with both having mean rating of 3.83.

Meanwhile, mean rating score for the contribution of electronic marketing strategy to the construction of effective role in customer satisfaction was 4.03 and high rating degree.

One sample T. test to identify statistical significance of electronic marketing strategy contribution to the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction was used, and its results are displayed in table (9).

Table (9) T-test results for sample responses on contribution of electronic marketing strategy in constructing effective role in customer's satisfactions

Hypothesis	Mean	S.D	T value	A F	Sig.	Result hypothesis accepted
Electronic marketing strategy contributes to the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction.	4.03	0.64	11.72	158	0.00	Accept the hypothesis

Table (9) showed that mean rating of electronic marketing strategy contribution to the construction of an effective role in customer's satisfaction was 4.03 with SD = 0.51, and a high rating degree, where value was 11.72 and this was statistically significant at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), hence the second hypothesis, of the study, was accepted, and consequently electronic marketing strategy contributed to the construction of on effective role in customers satisfaction to a high degree.

Results

1. Zein company management has a role in increasing customers number through maintenance and improvement of quality to a high degree.
2. Management do give customers a role in formulating quality strategy and their opinions and suggestions are considered when setting the strategic plan.
3. Management considered customer as main axis to depend on in achieving quality strategy.
4. Electronic marketing strategy contributed to the construction of an effective role in customers satisfaction to a high degree.
5. In their electronically work, employees emphasize on distinctive loyalty to their company and improving its image in customers minds.
6. Focusing on electronic marketing is among the important strategies employed by management to minimize many waste and improving its image in customers mind.

Recommendations

In light of the above results, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Continuous upgrading of the level of services provided to customers and never let competitors exceed the company to which they work.
2. Training of employees and holding courses in methods of dealing with customers.
3. Attending to set customer services with minimum cost, time and effort.
4. Increasing productivity quality provided maintains product quality.
5. Focusing on giving customers the good impression that his visit to the company site and dealing electronically with them are important for the customers.
6. Providing distinguished electronic services which satisfy customers and had more dimension than competitors.
7. Electronically responding to customers objection and questions quickly, dealing with and threat them instantly.
8. Increasing focus of electronic marketing which is the real interpreter of customers' needs and wants.
9. Expansion of electronic marketing process so that it can be treated which allow the possibility for its change in response to clients tastes change.

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